

Submitted month 36

Due month 36

Grant Agreement number 649416

H2020-YOUNG-SOCIETY-2014

PARTISPACE Project: Spaces and styles of participation
Formal, Non formal and informal possibilities of young
people’s participation in European cities

Deliverable n° 7.4: European Policy and Research Conference

Start date of project: May 1st 2015

Duration: 36 months

Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Andreas Walther

University of Frankfurt

Project co-funded by the European Commission within the Horizon 2020 programme		
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

WP7 – Dissemination and Communication activities
European Policy and Research Conference
EHESP, FRANCE

Authors: all the consortium

Finalised version: 27th April 2018

Table of contents

- 1. **History table** 4
- 2. **Project documentation sheet** 5
- 3. **Aim of this document**..... 6
- 4. **Organisation of the conference** 6
 - 1. Agenda/leaflet of the conference 7
 - 2. Booklet of conference speakers 8
 - 3. Description of the public 12
 - 4. Pictures 13
 - 5. Annexes including attendance list and power point presentations..... 18

1. History table

Version	Modification	Date	Authors
1	Document creation	25/04/2018	Céline MARTIN
2	Revision 1	26/04/2018	Anais MAINFRAY and Céline MARTIN
3	Last updates	27/04/2018	Anais MAINFRAY

2. Project documentation sheet

Project acronym	PARTISPACE
Project Full Title	Spaces and styles of participation: Formal, Non formal and informal possibilities of young people's participation in European cities
Grant Agreement	649416
Call Identifier	YOUNG-5a-2014
Topic	Societal and political engagement of young people and their perspectives on Europe
Funding Scheme	REA, European Commission (Horizon 2020)
Project Duration	36 months (May 2015 - April 2018)
Project objectives	The project Spaces and Styles of Participation (PARTISPACE) starts from the assumption that all young people do participate while not all participation is recognised as such. The study asks for the different ways in which young people participate in decisions which concern them and, in general, the life of their communities: How do 15-30-year-olds engage with the public in formal, non-formal and informal settings and how is this supported or inhibited by local youth policies and youth work?
Coordinator	Prof. Dr. Andreas Walther Goethe Universität Frankfurt am Main—Department of Educational Sciences Theodor-W.-Adorno-Platz 6 60629 Frankfurt am Main, Germany Phone +49 69 798 36416 a.walther@em.uni-frankfurt.de
Consortium partners	Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main (GUF), Germany Ecole des Hautes Etudes en Santé Publique (EHESP), France University of Cergy Pontoise (UCP), France Manchester Metropolitan University (MMU), UK University of Huddersfield (HUD), UK University of Bologna (UNIBO), Italy University of Gothenburg (UGOT), Sweden New Europe Centre for Regional Studies (NEC), Bulgaria Yeditepe University (YU), Turkey University of Applied Sciences St. Gallen (FHS), Switzerland

3. Aim of this document

The purpose of the European policy and research conference aims to describe and give an overview of the final research conference of Partispace project entitled Youth Participation in Europe: Diversity, (Mis)Recognition and (In)visibility, held in Paris on Wednesday 18th April 2018 at the French school of public health.

4. Organisation of the conference

In the presence of the European Commission (REA), European research stakeholders, policy makers and practitioners in the field of youth, the conference was aimed to disseminate and discuss the final results of the research including implications for policy and practice.

Experts' discussants as well as members of local advisory boards in each partner's cities were invited to put the results into perspective and enrich the findings.

Some young people who were interviewed in the frame of the research were also invited to discuss with the public (have a look at the booklet of conference speakers).

The report consists in the following:

- Agenda/leaflet of the conference
- Booklet of conference speakers
- Description of the public
- Pictures
- Annexes including attendance list and power point presentations

1. Agenda/leaflet of the conference

VENUE

Maison des sciences de l'Homme - Paris Nord
EHESP 20 Avenue George Sand, 93210 Plaine Saint Denis

By metro -

Take the line 12 in the direction Aubervilliers and get off at the terminus Front Populaire. 1st escalator : Take the exit 3 (sortie 3) – Maison des Sciences de l'Homme. Outside the metro, turn right to the Avenue George Sand, follow the street and walk about 2 minutes. On the right you will find a big black building George Sand.

By RER B and bus 139 or 239 -

Take the RER B and get off at the station La Plaine- Stade de France. Take the bus 139 in the direction Porte de la Villette or the bus 239 in the direction Rosa Parks. Get off at the station : Métallurgie

The George Sand's building is just in front of the bus station

By RER and bus 239 -

Take the RER B and get off at the station La Plaine- Stade de France

Take the bus 239 in the direction Rosa Parks

Get off at the 4 rd station called: Métallurgie

The George Sand's building is just in front of the bus station

INFO & REGISTRATIONS

Coordinator: Prof. Dr. Andreas Walther
(Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main)

Due to limited place early registration is strongly recommended to ensure participation.

No registration fee

Registration [here](#) until 31th March 2018

Practical information:

Anaïs Mainfray
EHESP Rennes
E-Mail: anaïs.mainfray@ehesp.fr

Céline Martin
Université de Cergy Pontoise
E-Mail: celine.Martin@ehesp.fr

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Youth Participation in Europe

Diversity

MisRecognition

InVisibility

Final conference of PARTISPACE

Paris, 18th April 2018

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649416

PARTISPACE PROJECT

There is a widespread assumption that young people's engagement with social issues and participation in the public sphere is decreasing, and that this drop is particularly prevalent in so-called disadvantaged groups. At the same time, what young people actually do in the public sphere in order to express themselves, to cope with their everyday lives, to realise their life plans, or to shape their environment, is only rarely understood and recognised as a form of participation.

The European research project Spaces and Styles of Participation. Formal, non-formal and informal possibilities of young people's participation in European cities (PARTISPACE) set out to challenge these assumptions and to explore these and other forms of youth participation. The general research interest was to examine if young people's practices in the public include much more participatory potential than widely assumed. The study's central research question was: **where and how do young people actually participate?**

During the conference findings will be presented and discussed. The aims are

- making young people's different ideas and practices of participation in society visible;
- assessing and challenging discourses of youth participation regarding their adequacy with regard to young people's needs and practices
- understanding what issues and forms of participation are relevant for different groups of young people;
- exploring how young people can be supported and empowered in their attempts to participate through policy and pedagogical practice.

PROGRAMME

09.30	WELCOMING COFFEE
10.30	OPENING Laurent Chambaud, <i>EHESP Rennes/Paris</i> Kerstin Wilde, <i>REA, Bruxelles</i> Andreas Walther, <i>Goethe-University of Frankfurt am Main</i>
11.00	PARTISPACE VIDEO
11.15	FINDINGS OF THE PARTISPACE PROJECT Chair: Valérie Becquet, <i>University Cergy-Pontoise</i> PARTISPACE OBJECTIVES AND DESIGN Axel Pohl, <i>Goethe-University Frankfurt am Main</i> LOCAL CONSTELLATIONS OF PARTICIPATION Demet Lüküklü, <i>Yeditepe University Istanbul</i> & Alexandre Pais, <i>Manchester Metropolitan University</i> Discussant: Enzo Mingione, <i>Università Milano-Bicocca</i> WHERE DO YOUNG PEOPLE PARTICIPATE? SPACES OF YOUTH PARTICIPATION Dominic Zimmermann, <i>University of Applied Sciences St. Gallen</i> , Björn Andersson, <i>Gothenburg University</i> , Valeria Pro, <i>University of Bologna</i> Discussant: Kirsi Paullina Kallio, <i>University of Tampere</i> HOW DO YOUNG PEOPLE PARTICIPATE? STYLES OF YOUTH PARTICIPATION Harriet Rowley, <i>Manchester Metropolitan University</i> Discussant: Yürük Kurkaran, <i>Istanbul Bilgi University Center for Civil Society Studies</i>
13.00	LUNCH
14.00	YOUNG PEOPLE'S PARTICIPATION BIOGRAPHIES Merena Ciconato, <i>University of Bologna</i> , Grainne McMahon, <i>Huddersfield University</i> Discussants: Pierre Durosov, <i>Keur Eskem association, Rennes</i> , Miryana Miteva, <i>Bauerzaks Foundation, Plovdiv</i> RE-THINKING YOUTH PARTICIPATION Andreas Walther, <i>Goethe-University of Frankfurt am Main</i>
15.10	Debate

15.20-15.40	COFFEE BREAK
15.40	IMPLICATIONS FOR POLICY & PRACTICE HOW DO YOUNG PEOPLE LEARN TO PARTICIPATE— AND HOW CAN LEARNING BE SUPPORTED? Barry Percy-Smith, <i>Huddersfield University</i> , Nigel Thomas, <i>University of Central Lancashire</i> Discussant: Martti Martinson, <i>SATO-Youth Participation & Information Resource Centre</i> WHAT CAN POLICY DO TO FACILITATE YOUTH PARTICIPATION? Janet Batsleer, <i>Manchester Metropolitan University</i> PANEL DISCUSSION: Maria Podlasek-Ziegler, <i>European Commission</i> , Rob O'Donnell, <i>OBESUJ</i> , Hasaan Amin, <i>Manchester Youth Council</i> , Björn Andersson, <i>Gothenburg University</i> , Sviya Kovacheva, <i>New Europe Centre Plovdiv</i> , Linda Kagerbauer, <i>Municipality of Frankfurt</i> Chair: Alice Anbarre, <i>Institute for Political Sciences - Rennes</i>
17.00	Debate
17.10	CONCLUSIONS Maria Podlasek-Ziegler, <i>European Commission</i> Andreas Walther, <i>Goethe-University of Frankfurt am Main</i>
17.30	END OF MEETING

2. Booklet of conference speakers

Laurent CHAMBAUD
EHESP, Rennes/Paris
Head of the French School of Public Health

Kerstin WILDE
REA, Brussels
Programme Advisor European Commission. Project officer of Partispace

Andreas WALTHER
Goethe-University - Frankfurt Main
Scientific coordinator of Partispace
Professor for education, social pedagogy and youth welfare at the Goethe University of Frankfurt.

Axel POHL
Goethe-University - Frankfurt Main
Dr coordination of Partispace
Researcher at Goethe University Frankfurt. He has been looking into participation mainly from a youth work and urban policy perspective.

Valérie BECQUET
University of Cergy- Pontoise
Professor, member of EMA, member for the team: citizenship, socialization, subjectivation process.

Demet LÜKÜSLÜ
University of Istanbul
Associate Professor and Director of Sociology Department at Yeditepe University, Istanbul. Demet's research focuses on the political participation of young people in Turkey.

Alexandre PAIS
Manchester Metropolitan University
Alexandre works in Manchester where he reads, writes and teaches about all aspects of educational research amenable to philosophical investigation.

Enzo MINGIONE

Professor Emeritus of Sociology at the University of Milan Bicocca. Member of the advisory board of Partispace.

Björn ANDERSSON

Gothenburg University Associate professor and senior lecturer in Social Work at The Department of Social Work. Björn has worked a lot on youth issues and on social work with young people.

Dominic ZIMMERMANN

University of Applied Sciences - St. Gallen. Sociologist and human geographer: his areas of expertise related to the project include social participation among youths, juvenile appropriation of urban spaces.

Valeria PIRO

University of Bologna Valeria Piro is currently a postdoctoral fellow at the Department of Sociology and Business Law of the University of Bologna.

Kirsi Pauliina KALLIO

University of Tampere Associate Professor, works currently at the Space and Political Agency Research Group (SPARG).

Harriet ROWLEY

Manchester Metropolitan University Lecturer in Education and Community, Faculty of Education, Harriet is an experienced qualitative researcher and teacher, working predominantly in low socio-economic status urban areas in the UK.

Yoruk KURTARAN

Istanbul Bilgi University Center for Civil Society Studies He received his BA and MA from Political Science and Public Administration Department. He has 20 years of professional experience working in several think tanks.

Morena CUCONATO

University of Bologna Associate Professor of Pedagogy and Social Pedagogy at the University of Bologna. Morena is interested in researching and exploring new meaning and setting of youth participation.

Grainne MCMAHON

Huddersfield University Senior Research Fellow at the University of Huddersfield. Grainne researches women, girls and feminism, and young people's social, cultural and political participation.

Pierre DUROSOY
Keur Eskemm association- Rennes
 One of the two coordinators of the Laboratoire Artistique et Populaire since 2015.

Miryana MITEVA
Bauersachs Foundation, Plovdiv
 Miryana is the executive director of Bauersachs Foundation since its establishment in 2013.

Martti MARTINSON
 Coordinator SÁLTO-Youth Participation & Information Resource Centre.

Barry PERCY-SMITH
University of Huddersfield.
 Director of the Centre for Applied Childhood Youth and Family Research. Previously worked with the SOLAR (Social and Organisational Learning as Action Research) in Bristol.

Nigel THOMAS
University of Central Lancashire, UK
 Professor Emeritus of Childhood and Youth, where he founded The Centre for Children and Young People's Participation. Expertise in child welfare, children's rights and participation.

Janet BATSLEER
Manchester Metropolitan University.
 Head of Centre of Childhood, Youth and Community. Reader in Education. Principal Lecturer Youth and Community Work.

Linda KAGERBAUER
 She is social worker, feminist and speaker and author. She works at the women's department in Frankfurt/ municipality of Frankfurt. There she is responsible for policies for girls.

Rob O'DONNELL
OBESSU
 Board Member of OBESSU, the umbrella organisation for school student unions and representative body for secondary students in Europe.

Hasaan AMIN
Youth Council, Manchester
 Hasaan is a dedicated youth politician and activist. He is an ex-youth councillor and is currently a Young Leader at the Manchester Youth Council.

Siyka KOVACHEVA

New Europe Centre for regional studies - Plovdiv

Senior researcher at the New Europe Centre Plovdiv, Associate Professor in Sociology and Social Policy and Vice-Dean of the Faculty of Philosophy and History.

Alice ANBERREE

IEP RENNES

Management Lecturer at Sciences Po Rennes in France. Her PhD thesis, defended in 2015 at Nantes University, focuses on audiences' participation in semi-public artistic venues.

Maria PODLASEK-ZIEGLER

Policy officer at the Directorate-General for Education and Culture, European Commission.

3. Description of the public

Total participants registered: 95

Total participants attending the conference: 72

Without members of the consortium, members of the advisory board and guests (discussant and chairing), 31 external participants from different countries and profiles attended the conference.

Among the 31 participants

Country	Number of participants	Position
France	12	6 students
		6 professionals in youth organization or research on youth
UK	7	professor , researcher, social workers and volunteers
Bulgaria	3	researcher and members of youth organization
Poland	2	youth policy maker and youth worker
Switzerland	3	students and policy maker
Turkey	2	students
Germany	1	student
Sweden	1	planning officer
Total	31	

4. Pictures

Aims and focus

- What are different local conditions of youth participation?
- How do local youth policies (and national welfare states) foster youth participation?
- How do formal settings of youth participation function – and what are their function in local constellations?

→ Data:

- National reports on youth policy and youth participation
- Mapping: expert interviews, group discussions with young people
- In-depth case studies of formal settings of youth participation

5. Annexes including attendance list and power point presentations

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris, 18th April 2018

Nom / Last Name	Prénom / First Name	Signature	Attestation de présence (cocher la case si besoin) / certificate of attendance (check the box if needed)
Aijmer	Paula		
Alkoç	Nursel		
Amberrée	Alice		
Amin	Hasaan		
Andersson	Björn		
Ansoborlo	Marie		
Bacqué	Marie-Hélène		
Barber	Patrick		
Batsleer	Janet		
Becevic	Zulmir		
Becquet	Valérie		
Boishardy	Yoann		
Bright	Geoff		
Cornu	Suzanne		
Cuconato	Morena		
Dagan	Modeste		
de Saint Pol	Thibaut		
Deffontaines	Violette		
Defrotin	Agathe		
Demoulin	Jeanne		
Didi	Naoufal		
Duggan	James		
Durosoy	Pierre		

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris, 18th April 2018

Nom / Last Name	Prénom / First Name	Signature	Attestation de présence (cocher la case si besoin) / certificate of attendance (check the box if needed)
Faysse	Marc		
Fuchs	Manuel		
Gasnier	Sylvie		
Ghio	Clara		
Grimaldi	Silvia		
Guliyev	Ziya		
Hamurcu	Sinan		
Hartmann	Sibille		
Henriksson	Kim		
Hiron	Morgane		
Hristozova	Darena		
Ikni	Anthony		
Ilardo	Marta		
Impastato	Caterina		
Issame	Marghich		
Kagerbauer	Linda		
Kalala Mabuluki	Etch		
Kallio	Kirsi Pauliina		
Kovacheva	Siyka		
Kucharska	Katarzyna		
Kurtaran	Yoruk Ilhan		

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris, 18th April 2018

Nom / Last Name	Prénom / First Name	Signature	Attestation de présence (cocher la case si besoin) / certificate of attendance (check the box if needed)
Labadie	Francine		
Lancien	Alice		
Larguèze	Denis		
Le Grand	Eric		
Lessaer	Bartek		
Liljeholm Hansson	Susanne		
Lüküslü	Demet		
Lütgens	Jessica		
Mainfray	Anaïs		
Martin	Céline		
Martinez	Cécile		
Martinson	Martti		
McDonnell	Jane		
McMahon	Grainne		
Mengilli	Yagmur		
Merchaoui	Liza		
Mingione	Enzo		
Miteva	Miryana		
Moran	Rhettta		
Nanov	Plamen		
O'Donnell	Rob		
Osmanoglu	Berrin		
Oumar Nangp	BA		

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649416

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris, 18th April 2018

Nom / Last Name	Prénom / First Name	Signature	Attestation de présence (cocher la case si besoin) / certificate of attendance (check the box if needed)
Pais	Alexandre		
Parisse	Jordan		
Percy-Smith	Barry		
Piro	Valeria		
Pitti	Ilaria		✓
Podlasek-Ziegler	Maria		
Pohl	Axel		
Popivanov	Boris		
Porte	Emmanuel		
Portefaix	Pauline		
Reutlinger	Christian		
Richez	Jean Claude		
Roth	Patricia		
Rowley	Harriet		
Savova	Yuliya		
Sesay	Benedikt		
Sibirský	Alexandr		
Siedykh	Daria		
Täubert	Dominic		
Thomas	Nigel		
Thoury	Claire		
Tsankova	Kremena		

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris, 18th April 2018

Nom / Last Name	Prénom / First Name	Signature	Attestation de présence (cocher la case si besoin) / certificate of attendance (check the box if needed)
Von Schwänenflügel	Larissa	<i>L. von Schwänenflügel</i>	
Walther	Andreas	<i>A. Walther</i>	
Wigger	Annegret	<i>A. Wigger</i>	
Wilde	Kerstin	<i>K. Wilde</i>	
Zimmermann	Dominic	<i>D. Zimmermann</i>	
Dijoux	Dominique	<i>D. Dijoux</i>	
Stuart	Dune	<i>D. Stuart</i>	
Smith	Reko	<i>R. Smith</i>	
CHARLES	CHRIS CHRISTIAN	<i>Chris Charles</i>	
Billu	Lea	<i>Lea Billu</i>	
MORRISON	Elaine	<i>E. Morrison</i>	

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Youth Participation in Europe

Diversity

MisRecognition

In Visibility

Final conference of PARTISPACE

Paris, 18th April 2018

EHESP

European
Commission

Greetings & Introduction

Laurent Chambaud
EHESP Rennes/Paris

Kerstin Wilde
REA Brussels

Andreas Walther
University Frankfurt

PARTI SPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Findings of PARTISPACE

Chair: Valérie Becquet
University Cergy-Pontoise

Partispace objectives and design

Local constellations of participation

**Where do young people participate?
Spaces of youth participation**

**How do young people participate?
Styles of youth participation**

**Young people's participation
*biographies***

Re-thinking youth participation

EHEP

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

European
Commission

Implications for Policy & Practice

Learning and participation – what
should practitioners know

Policy recommendations

Panel discussion

Chair: *Alice Anberrée*
Sciences Po Rennes

Conclusions and outlook

PARTI SPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

PARTISPACE video

**Compiled from self-
documentations of action research
projects by/with youth people**

**Denis Larcher, *EHESP Rennes*
Céline Martin, *EHESP Rennes*
Zulmir Becevic, *Univ. Gothenburg***

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

PARTISPACE

Objectives and Design

Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition,
(In)Visibility

Final conference of PARTISPACE, Saint-Denis, 18 April 2018

Axel Pohl

Goethe University **Frankfurt am Main** and University of Applied Sciences **Sankt Gallen**

Outline

1. Starting points

2. Objectives

3. Methodology

STARTING POINTS

Research on youth participation

Research on youth participation

→ Participation is good. The more the better

Research on youth participation

- Participation is good. The more the better
- Participation is decreasing or becoming more difficult

Research on youth participation

- Participation is good. The more the better
- Participation is decreasing or becoming more difficult
- There are specific desirable forms and contexts: civic and political life, local communities, representative democracy, youth organisations

Research on youth participation

- Participation is good. The more the better
- Participation is decreasing or becoming more difficult
- There are specific desirable forms and contexts: civic and political life, local communities, representative democracy, youth organisations
- Young people are not able and well-informed, they need to be encouraged and educated

European discourses on youth participation

Cf. Becquet, Kovacheva, Popivanov and Kabaivanov (2016), European discourses on youth participation and their national interpretation in the countries-members of the Partispace project (Work Package 3).

YOUNG-5a-2014: Societal and political engagement of young people and their perspectives on Europe

[To explore] the perspectives of young people on Europe and the ways in which they engage in shaping its future is crucial for the long-term success of the European project. ... The EU Youth Strategy aims to encourage young people to be active citizens and participate in society ... In this context it is important to understand how young people participate in the society under unequal conditions and expectations, express their views ... and advocate their interests which may involve new forms of political and civic actions ... Research will analyse the reasons for the declining trust ... It will also examine how best to stimulate the societal and political engagement of young people ... [and] the different ways ... in which young people engage in society, exploring the socio-cultural and generational contexts ... In addition, research should explore which of these forms have been successful in achieving societal goals ...

OBJECTIVES

Objectives

To develop a concept of participation starting from

Objectives

To develop a concept of participation starting from

→ what young people do in and/or in relation to the public

Objectives

To develop a concept of participation starting from

- what young people do in and/or in relation to the public
- what it means to them

Objectives

To develop a concept of participation starting from

- what young people do in and/or in relation to the public
- what it means to them
- and how these practices are recognised, ignored or facilitated by policy, authorities and educational practice

Objectives

To develop a concept of participation starting from

- what young people do in and/or in relation to the public
- what it means to them
- and how these practices are recognised, ignored or facilitated by policy, authorities and educational practice

Research question

HOW and WHERE do young people participate across social milieus and youth cultural scenes?

METHODOLOGY

Quote from project proposal

“The methodological approach ... is characterised by an empirical analysis of different individual and collective practices, their biographical and cultural relevance, their social contextualisation ... and their political recognition ... The design should ... allow[ing] young people to co-define what participation is from their perspective.”

Quote from project proposal

“The methodological approach ... is characterised by an empirical analysis of different individual and collective practices, their biographical and cultural relevance, their social contextualisation ... and their political recognition ... The design should ... allow[ing] young people to co-define what participation is from their perspective.”

This implies:

Quote from project proposal

“The methodological approach ... is characterised by an empirical analysis of different individual and collective practices, their biographical and cultural relevance, their social contextualisation ... and their political recognition ... The design should ... allow[ing] young people to co-define what participation is from their perspective.”

This implies:

→ watching, listening, asking, trying to understand

Quote from project proposal

“The methodological approach ... is characterised by an empirical analysis of different individual and collective practices, their biographical and cultural relevance, their social contextualisation ... and their political recognition ... The design should ... allow[ing] young people to co-define what participation is from their perspective.”

This implies:

- watching, listening, asking, trying to understand
- openness rather than pre-defined indicators

Quote from project proposal

“The methodological approach ... is characterised by an empirical analysis of different individual and collective practices, their biographical and cultural relevance, their social contextualisation ... and their political recognition ... The design should ... allow[ing] young people to co-define what participation is from their perspective.”

This implies:

- watching, listening, asking, trying to understand
- openness rather than pre-defined indicators
- research strategy ,led‘ and influenced by young people

Research design

WP 1 Management

Administrative management, communication and knowledge management, monitoring, organisation of meetings, preparation and launch

WP 2 National contexts:

Literature review, discourse analysis, policy examples, Description of studied cities

WP 3 European context

Discourse analysis, analysis of European Social Survey

WP 4 Local case studies

Mapping

Group discussions and city walks with young people (N=15 per city, ca. 100 in total, involving 300-500 young persons)
Expert interviews with key persons and stakeholders (N=20 per city; ca. 150 in total)

Reconstruction

In-depth case studies of formal, non-formal and informal settings (N=6 per city, total 42)
Analysis of individual participation biographies (N=12 per city, 72 in total)

Analysis of local case studies

WP 5 Action research with young people

Encouraging and assisting young people in own research integrated with local case studies

WP 6 Analysis

working groups on:

- Comparative analysis of survey, national contexts, local constellations
- Thematic analysis of formality, practices and forms, biographies, activation

Validation with local actors incl. young people

WP 7 Dissemination

Youth conference(s), EU policy conference, research papers, films, training module, European and local advisory groups, policy brief

Cities

Research steps within each city

Mapping of youth participation in the 8 cities

- expert interviews
- group discussions and city walks with young people

48 case studies of participatory settings

- ethnographic field work
- biographical interviews

Participatory action research with young people

- promoting young people's participation
- empowering them as co-researchers

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Research approach

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Research approach

→ between open and 'grounded'

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Research approach

- between open and 'grounded'
- reconstructive

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Research approach

- between open and 'grounded'
- reconstructive
- multiperspectival – multilevel – multisited

Summing up

Objects of research

practices – biographies – discourses – institutions – relations
of power and recognition

Research approach

- between open and 'grounded'
- reconstructive
- multiperspective – multilevel – multisited
- comparative

Fruitful debates!

Fruitful debates!

Fruitful debates!

Stay in touch!

axel.pohl@fhsg.ch

www.partispace.eu

Fruitful debates!

Stay in touch!

axel.pohl@fhsg.ch

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Local Constellations of Youth Participation in Comparative Perspective

Demet Lüküslü
Alexandre Pais

*“Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition, (In)Visibility”,
Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris 18th of April 2018*

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Aims and focus

- What are different local conditions of youth participation?
- How do local youth policies (and national welfare states) foster youth participation?
- How do formal settings of youth participation function – and what are their function in local constellations?

→ Data:

- National reports on youth policy and youth participation
- Mapping: expert interviews, group discussions with young people
- In-depth case studies of formal settings of youth participation

Dimensions of difference between local (youth policy) constellations

- **Socio-economic situation**
 - Young people's life conditions, local budget for youth policy
- **Welfare state approach**
 - Regulation of access to social security and education/training (universal, individual choice etc.)
- **Youth policy infrastructures**
 - Specialised departments? Youth work infrastructure or single projects?
- **Youth policy responsiveness**
 - Flexibility, reflexivity and openness of youth policy for changes & initiatives
- **Counter-initiatives**
 - How is particular youth policy reflected by (informal) counter-initiatives?
- **Formal settings of youth participation at municipality level?**

Key differences between local constellations

	Bologna	Eski-sehir	Frankfurt	Gothenburg	Manchester	Plovdiv	Rennes	Zurich
Socio-economic situation	Medium	Medium	Rich	Medium	Medium	Poor	Medium	Rich
Welfare state	Under-institutionalised	Transformation	Conservative	Universalistic	Liberal	Transformation	Conservative	Conservative
Youth policy infrastructure	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes/No	No	Yes/No	Yes
Youth policy responsiveness	High	Low	Medium	High	Low	Low	Low	High
Formal settings	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes/No	Yes
Counter initiatives	Distrust	Distrust	Distrust	Trust	Distrust	Distrust	Depends on milieu	Trust

Formal settings of youth participation

- **Different types:**
 - Youth councils: Frankfurt, Gothenburg, Manchester
 - Student councils: Plovdiv, Zurich
 - Residential care home council: Frankfurt
 - Extra-curricular citizenship education in school: Bologna
 - Formal youth (information) centres: Eskisehir, Rennes
- **Dimensions of analysis**
 - Organisation, roles and mandates
 - Positioning of formal participation between adults and youth
 - Topics and processes of agenda setting
 - Biographical constellations of involvement

Positioning and agenda setting between adults and young people

2 exemplary contrasting quotations for positioning/agenda setting

- **Example for pre-defined and controlled through pedagogical methods (reflecting a hermetic environment of educating 'good citizens'):**

“There is a youth work ‘cult’ of ice breakers and games as ‘participatory engagement toolkits’ ... Although the discussion is made by young people, the entire structure is determined by others beforehand. It is as if there was a fear of getting lost in the discussion if given to young people’s own initiative, thus the need to control it by elaborating a set of specific rules that groups have to follow (cover certain topics, make a report, report back to one person in the group, etc.) ... There is a list of campaigns like ‘Mental Health’, ‘Don’t hate educate’ and ‘Curriculum for life’ on the agenda and there will be others emerging as a result of a ballot.” (field note youth council 1)

- **Example for conflictual negotiation (reflecting legitimization dilemma between youth and adults):**

“The president introduces an extra topic: he has been invited to a district committee meeting concerning the annual ‘school is out-drinking’ as many neighbours feel disturbed ... Council members react annoyed as the event is only once a year ... The adult consultant intervenes. According to him, it was a mistake going there and even organizing another meeting ... The president moans, he will do it anyway, the other members agree, in the end they are the youth council ... The president reports, strange ideas had been raised like obliging students to clean up the park or even making them pay. The consultant tries to intervene once more. He wants to prevent a political mistake but he does not succeed, the meeting will take place.” (field note, youth council 2)

Patterns of local constellations and formal youth participation

- *Recognizing and addressing* (Gothenburg):
 - Young people are recognised (and addressed) as co-citizens, participation well-equipped and embedded in responsive youth policy infrastructure
- *Assigning a role* (Frankfurt, Zurich):
 - Youth policy infrastructure, partly responsive, young people addressed with regard to specific roles (students) → limited youth participation
- *Providing without promoting* (Plovdiv, Zurich):
 - Representation and services within a given institutional setting, in some cases the only formal setting of representation
- *Leading the process from above* (Frankfurt (care home), Eskisehir, Manchester, Rennes, Zurich)
 - Agenda is pre-defined, strong paternalistic and pedagogising approach
- *Leaving them in autonomy without power* (Bologna, Plovdiv):
 - Friendly dialogue with youth initiatives but no infrastructure and mechanism of influence

Functions and power relationships

Legitimising institutional control and normalisation of youth

- Student & care home councils councils (Plovdiv, Zurich, Frankfurt)

Crisis management

- With reference to former riots and protest (Zurich, to some extent Eskişehir but especially Bologna)

Disavowal of adult responsibility, crisis management

- Rennes, Manchester, Zurich or Frankfurt

Creating a world of politics without the political

- Youth councils (Frankfurt, Gothenburg, Manchester), Student councils (Plovdiv, Zurich)

Designing and Displaying “empowered young people ” and “good citizens”

- Youth councils (Gothenburg, Manchester, Frankfurt)

Fun and growth-why (some) young people enjoy formal participation

- Youth councils (in particular Gothenburg)

Conclusions

- There are differences between local contexts shaped by money, youth policy infrastructure/responsiveness
 - ... while influence of national welfare state indirect
 - ... but clear influence of shift towards activating welfare state
- Formal participants as ideal entrepreneurs of the self
 - The more youth policy empower youth participation – the more they subject young people to adult habitus?
- Should they stay away? No, but
 - possibilities of representation that are open for negotiation
 - embedded in responsive youth work infrastructure

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Appropriating the PartiCity

Spatial Dynamics of Youth Participation

Thematic group 'Space':

Björn Andersson, Gothenburg

Nicola De Luigi, Bologna

Valeria Piro, Bologna

Christian Reutlinger, Zürich

Dominic Zimmerman, Zürich

The concept of space

- Materiality, the physical world
- The social construction of space
- Social relations
- Social processes
- Bodily appearance, embodiment

Where do young people participate?

Principally everywhere!

The background features four overlapping circles in light blue, light green, light yellow, and light red, arranged in a circular pattern.

Appropriation of space

- Concrete action, 'work the space'
- Active process, changing both the subject and the object
- Place-making
- Meaning-making

Place-making as home-making

- *I have to paint or tag something where I feel at home, where I pass by often, where I know more about the place, where you feel more at home (Graffiti writer Frankfurt).*
- *... it's like a home what you have here, you are actually at home, you behave like you're at home... (Girls group Frankfurt).*

Merging the boundaries between public and private, formal and informal.

Meaning-making

Everywhere around - the walls, counters, windows and doors - there are newspaper cuttings, drawings, poetry, banners, and photographs which bring HIDDEN's work and history alive. In that sense, HIDDEN feels like a living and unique entity in its basement (WP5-report Manchester).

- transforming the material environment
- attributing a shared set of meanings
- building identity

Contesting the already given meanings

You can't be up there! (Angry bystander to parkour traceurs Gothenburg)

... this situation dates back to 20-30 years ago (...) the city was divided into neighbourhoods, the political view could change when you cross a bridge (...). So you can feel this with your audience (Street musicians Eskisehir).

Adding new meanings, sometimes conflictual.

Public space - messages

Since March 36 (April 5), in Rennes, citizens opposed to the Labor Law are assembling Place du Peuple (formerly [or officially] Place Charles de Gaulle) to re-appropriate politics, invent another relationship with the public space and deepen democracy (Nuit Debout Rennes).

Public space as 'agora' or 'participatory space'.

Public space - meetings

The weather was very sunny and despite being a workday the square was full of young people. They were scattered around the cafes, part of them visiting the nearby bookstores while others were just standing in the sun (Field notes Plovdiv).

Public space and sociability.

Public space - makings

That's really what it's all about, that you are prepared in whatever way and know exactly: How does a surface react? What's this like, what's that like? (Parkour Zürich).

Public space and action. Space-making.

Frontstage - backstage

... we want to bring out the contradictions (...). For this reason the protests on the street go hand in hand with the daily life of the dormitory (Social Centre Bologna).

Public – semi-public – private. Multilayered spaces.

Space and participation

- Invited and popular spaces – merging boundaries
- Different kinds of voicing
- Taking part in the city – meanings and belongings to places
- Virtual space

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

How do young people participate? Styles of youth participation

Harriet Rowley

*“Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition, (In)Visibility”,
Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris 18th of April 2018*

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Aims and Focus

How and where do 15 to 30 year-old young people participate across social milieus and youth cultural scenes in eight European cities, framed by different national welfare, education and youth policies?

- Comparative concept of 'style' - How do young people experience participation in relation to their living conditions, socio-cultural backgrounds, and local contexts of engagement?

In relation to starting assumption of PARTISPACE – issue of recognition

- How do young people use agency to engage in processes of innovation or re-signification of accepted and non-accepted forms of practice and what struggles over recognition emerge for different styles of participation?

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

State of the art

Participation

- Public discourse – ‘status’ than as a ‘lived practice’ (Lister 2008).
- ‘Conceptual confusion’ (Ekman and Amna 2012)
- Dissatisfaction/changing lifestyles = alternative modes/reinvention of civic space.
- Key features – hybridity between social, civic and political forms.

Styles

- Concept most commonly used in literature on youth subcultures
- Definition: interpret simply as forms or what people ‘do’, structured by social position.
- Importance of intension behind the performance – recognised and emerging forms operating between boundaries.

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Methodology

Rationale for sampling of cases

- Use of heuristic – formal, informal and non-formal for case selection.
- Conceptualisation of style combines individual expression with social and collective interests on a continuum of positions determined by contextual factors.

Recognised forms	Non-recognised forms
<ol style="list-style-type: none">1. Youth council, Gothenburg and charity for homeless men, Manchester – <i>class divisions</i>.2. Humanitarian NGO, Eskisehir and self-organised centre, Bologna – <i>volunteering</i>.	<p>Non-recognised forms</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none">3. Alternative popular education, Rennes and Music scene, Plovdiv – <i>culture/art</i>4. Graffiti Sprayers, Frankfurt and Ultra's, Bologna – <i>Youth cultures</i>

Main Findings

- **The concept of style enables us to explore the contents behind recognised forms of participation as well as those not commonly recognised as participation.**

Example of recognised form - Gothenburg Youth council - reflective of social context.

“it benefits me as a person a lot and I know that everyone who has been involved in the council that I know thinks the same. So, this is not just a good foundation for the future, it’s like a good now, a very good now, it is incredibly developing”

Example of unrecognised form – Graffiti Sprayers – artistic form of political expression

“graffiti is basically political, it’s in its nature, because it questions the right of private property, every graffiti is political, even if it’s not intentionally political [...] it expresses a resistance with colour against the state authority”

Main Findings

- **Young people re-signify and re-appropriate practices to suit their own means and competencies.**

Example of recognised form: Humanitarian NGO, Eskisehir/Social centre, Bologna

“If politics harm people, polarize people, it is not a good thing. Today, politics polarize people. If one day there is some kind of politics which unify people, which involves respect for different views, then I would do politics.”

- **Struggle over recognition provides opportunity for informal learning but also compromise**

Example of unrecognised form: Alternative popular education, Rennes.

“Elected officials and bureaucrats for the city X, at the beginning, they nearly laughed at us initially... Now, they are asking us to be part of plenty of projects, they are chasing after us (laughs).”

- **Participation is relational - process of sense-making with others**

“We were all born to this world the same and we all take nothing with us. We need to remember that our actions count more than our words.”

Conclusions

- Hybrid and diverse ways that young people ‘do’ participation.
- Differences in chosen forms of expressions dependent on means and competencies but also reflective of social positions/structural constraints.
- Common challenge - issues of (mis) recognition.
- Claims for visibility work on a cognitive and emotional level – show emerging critiques and new possibilities for civic action.
- Future youth policy foster experiments of resignification – importance of ‘lived practice’ or participation through doing.

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Biographical analysis of young people's participation

Gráinne McMahon
Morena Cuconato

*“Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition, (In)Visibility”,
Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris 18th of April 2018*

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Aims and data

- Exploring participatory activities over the course of young people's lives and young people's meaning-making of participation in terms of their biographies
- **Data:**
 - 96 biographies in all (broadly two per case study)
 - 16 biographies translated for analysis (eight young women, eight young men)
 - All cities, full age range of project

Research questions

- To understand *why* and *how* young people become active participants within their lives, what motivates them to do so, and what experiences and structures lead to certain participative activities (or not):
 1. What makes and distinguishes routes into/ careers of participation?
 2. What are the relationships between participation and other areas of life?
- Clusters of participation careers and dimensions of participation biographies

‘Clusters of participation careers’

- Socio-cultural and economic conditions, learning processes, and biographical turning points:
 - Fighting for justice from inside the system
 - Being a conformist for change
 - Personal and professional development by care for others
 - Experimenting with new paths for change

‘Dimensions of participation biographies’

- Biographical experiences expressed in participation and meaning-making of participation:
- Involvement in:
 - participatory activities to secure recognition in identity work
 - participatory activities as an expression of self-efficacy
 - different participatory activities as expression of experiences with institutions
 - participatory activities to cope with harmful experiences
 - participatory activities as positioning between youth culture and adult habitus

‘Betty’, 27, Zurich: ‘Conformist for change’

- Socially moderate background; non-rebellious and smooth school path (invested in education)
- ‘Late-comer’ to participation (early 20s) – political activism
- **Turning points:**
 - Political campaigning (Scottish Referendum)
 - Finding autonomous (political) space

- **Learning processes:**

‘I realized or accepted a bit that capitalism and the systems we have now, for me, well, it doesn’t work. That doesn’t mean that I really want a revolution.... But, yes, slowly I got there that I think, yeah, really different.’

↑ Fighting injustice through cooperation:

Betty: activities as an expression of self-efficacy

- Family difficulties with illness (mother and brother); school and book as comfort zone
- World-oriented attitude leading her to a wider variety of participatory paths; apparently by coincidence
- (Comparatively) later development of personal values development; sensitisation to problem of injustice and discrimination.
- Professional choices that have the moral benefit of doing something good as added value.
- Joy of working together with *“like-minded”* people:
‘You can achieve a lot more with others and sometimes it is much more fun as well.’

‘Mario’, 24, Plovdiv: Experimenting with new paths for change

- Wealthy background, lived abroad, experienced different schools, good achievement. However. Disconnect from peers: *‘I could not quickly fit into the mode of communication, I mean interests of people [...] Some of them were just plainly rejecting me.’*
- **Turning points:**
 - Entering graffiti scene
 - Founding autonomous (cultural) space with friend
- **Learning processes:**
- *‘Negligence means lack of information, and lack of information leads to distorted and most often wrong opinion.’*
 - ➔ Combining his rational but *‘soulless’* engagement as law student with understanding how society and politics work, and desire to create a better world through promoting cultural space of free speech, political discussion and information networking

‘Mario’: identity-diversification/ change

- Early involvement in graffiti culture, interest in cultural-spaces, ideologically-driven
- Informal participatory space (music and cultural centre) allows for:
 - identity-diversification/ change (‘second’ identity);
 - opportunity to bring about political change (self-efficacy);
 - a space in which to ‘fit’, and pursue youth cultural interests (and ensure recognition and belonging) and feeling *‘complete as a human being [...] more filled with emotion.’*

Youth interests and needs emerged so far:

Belonging and recognition

- Visibility
- Personal development and change

Politically-minded

- Justice, fairness, equality
- Ideological

Expression

- ‘Safe space’
- Experimentation

Autonomy

Identity-work

- Finding voice
- Meaningful and deliberate (chosen) participation

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Re-Thinking Youth Participation

Andreas Walther

*“Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition, (In)Visibility”,
Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris 18th of April 2018*

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Back to aim and research question

Research interest: Is there a relation between the apparent lack of youth participation and prevalence of ideological and discursive limitations of what is recognised as participation?

Do we need a modified and extended concept of participation that takes social change into account and does not exclude lived practice of young people – *and what would such a concept entail?*

Research question: *HOW and WHERE do young people participate differently across social milieus and youth cultural scenes and across eight European cities?*

What is recognised as participation?

Summarising PARTISPACE findings

- *Discourse* addresses young people
 - as future citizens ... but incomplete (with deficits) → ,in the making‘
 - needing education for ,involvement in something‘ → pedagogisation
- (Local) *Contexts* make a difference
 - socio-economic contexts, welfare states, local youth policies
 - formal youth participation (more/less) power → forms adult habitus
- Participation is situated in social space
 - but also structuring social space
 - appropriation of (public) space as claim/attempt of being/taking part
- Participation occurs in different styles
 - social positioning, youth cultures, identities → adaptation, identification, resistance
- Participation emerges from/in/as subjective *biographies*
 - different ways into/through different forms of participation
 - interplay between life (dis)course, subjective meaning and public space

Conclusions and perspectives

1. Participation is not an individual act – but a relational practice
2. Participation implies recognition by ‘others’ (Honneth)
 - Some practices are recognised as participation – others not
→ unequal power and recognition
 - Some young people make more experiences of recognition in their lives than others
 - self-confidence and self-efficacy of being able to make a difference
 - more or less subjective relevance of public space and public institutions

Conclusions and perspectives

3. Recognition of participation requires distinction
politics ≠ political, civil society ≠ civic
 - Everyday life practice as „micro-politics“ (Deleuze & Guattari)
 - political acts deriving from ‚desire‘ not classified by official discourse
 - coping with everyday lives as claim of being/taking part
 - Politics as „police“ excluding acts that cannot be classified as political – the political as conflict and dissent (or „noise“; Rancière)
 - The Political not only as spoken but also „embodied acts“ – public space not only as ordered but as „space of appearance“ (Butler)
 - ‚in presence of others who see what we see and hear what we hear“ (Arendt)
 - ‚outside‘ (as many young people would say)
 - The Political as contesting the occupation of „empty space of power“ from the margins of Politics/Society/Civil Society (Lefort)
 - The Political as struggle for hegemony (Gramsci) and recognition (Honneth)

Conclusions and perspectives

4. Opening representative democracy and institutionalised welfare state towards „Radical Democracy“ (Laclau & Mouffe)
 - extending recognition of participation and of the Political
 - contesting established boundaries at least as important as maintaining order to prevent exclusion

→ Youth participation may be understood as ...

- Relational
- Recognition
- Political ≠ Politics (may include everyday life participation)
- Conflict

**Youth Participation in Europe:
Diversity, (Mis)recognition, (In)visibility
Final conference of *Partispace*
Paris, 18^{me} Avril 2018**

Learning from, and about, young people's participation

Nigel Thomas (University of Central Lancashire)

Barry Percy-Smith (University of Huddersfield)

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

www.partispace.eu

Learning from – and about – young people’s participation

Work Package 5: Youth-Led Action Research Projects

Deliverable 7.2: Training module for youth workers and students

Work Package 5: Youth-Led Action Research Projects

- Action research projects devised and led by groups of young people, facilitated and supported by the Partispace national teams.
- Mainly took place in the latter stages of the Partispace research, following the case study research in WP4.
- Most projects involved groups with whom we had worked in WP4.
- There were 18 projects across the eight cities. Their character and purpose varied widely – we identified four general categories.

The ARPs – character of the 18 projects

- **Struggles for inclusion and justice:** projects that sought recognition for a particular group of young people (such as refugees) as members of society with rights, needs and contributions to make.
- **Articulating values and identities:** projects in which ‘sub-cultural’ groups of young people (such as graffiti artists) appeared to be ‘navigating the margins’ of mainstream society to find ways of articulating their own values and identities.
- **Finding solutions to social problems:** projects that addressed particular social issues concerning young people, whether or not they had a personal stake in them or were acting out of altruism.
- **Peer activation and engagement:** projects that focused on encouraging and supporting young people to engage in participatory activities and tackling barriers to their participation.

So what did we learn?

- Relevance, immediacy and the importance of context
- Seeking recognition and communicating lived experience
- Sociality of participation
- Motivation and commitment
- Autonomy and self-determination
- Leadership and group dynamics
- Working together in new ways
- Ambivalence and discomfort

Relevance, immediacy and the importance of context

- Many young people feel strongly about a range of issues in society – social justice, caring for people – yet are most likely to mobilise around issues that are close to their everyday lives.
- Most of these projects had clear relevance to young people’s own lives, directly for themselves and those close to them, or indirectly through what they see around them.
- This relevance and immediacy has a bearing on how young people participate. Participation becomes a lived social practice – ‘participation for real’ – rather than a performance in a context abstracted from their everyday lives.

Seeking recognition – communicating lived experience

- For many young people the priority is to express who they are, to communicate lived realities and be valued – participation as a *struggle for recognition*. This is not about *representing* interests or perspectives, but participating as active citizens, contributing to the social fabric of the city through their activities.
- Using artistic and cultural forms such as parkour or graffiti, rather than more formal processes, allows young people to express themselves in ways that have meaning for them. Young people may also use these forms to build neighbourhood solidarity as part of a struggle against a system experienced as unjust and oppressive.

“Perhaps the most important thing is trying to build a group with a pleasant atmosphere. To build that kind of environment a person wants to go to. So, we firstly have to build a real community, because to be active, to participate, doesn’t mean just to come here and say your idea, but it also means to free ourselves from stereotypes, to take a stand, to feel included – from coming into a place that seems boring at first, but then lets you discover the wonder, the amazement of staying together...”

Social and political dimensions

- Although participation often has a ‘political’ character, running through all the projects was an inherent sociality.
- Some groups are formed with a clear social intent, but even those that are more overtly change-oriented retain a fundamental social dimension.
- Sometimes ‘social’ participation becomes political as a group struggles for a space where they can follow their interests.

“We found that very often young people’s participation is about everyday activities of self-discovery, identity formation rather than reaching concrete results which is contrary to the expectations and bureaucratic requirements of administrative bodies of policy making.”

Motivation and commitment

- Young people had no shortage of ideas and inspiration, but for some groups converting this into action and sustaining commitment became more problematic, resulting in falling short of their aims, or even in complete withdrawal.
- In projects where the motivation to participate was rooted in their own personal struggles, commitment tended to be less of a problem.

Autonomy and self-determination

- Young people expressed a desire to do things for themselves, rather than be 'done to' – to have freedom to experiment, learn from experience and be creative.

“I like how we have the freedom, we don't get controlled by it ... the [youth] council can be a bit tokenistic, like we have something on the agenda then someone high up puts something on the agenda. We just want the chance of being independent ... it's important to have independence – it's a learning curve.”

- On the other hand young people were open about seeking support and input from adults as and when they felt they needed it. They do not always see the professional role as oppressive and controlling, but value collaborative relationships with adults.

Leadership and group dynamics

- Many groups evinced a democratic orientation based on consensus and absence of hierarchy. There was a commitment among young people to share, respect each other's contributions and engage in collective processes.
- In reality such horizontal power relations were sometimes difficult to sustain. Instead, in many projects individuals emerged as leaders and acted in ways that often mirrored adult leadership of young people's groups.

Working together in new ways

- The fundamental principle of action research is that participants are active in researching and making sense of their own realities.
- Democratisation of the research process – the ‘adult’ researcher is no longer the expert controlling the project, but instead a supporter, enabler and facilitator of learning.
- Power is at the heart of participation. The shift in power relationships between adult researchers and young people provided an opportunity for learning.

“It is easier when action comes from young people. The risk is to be dominant in the process. Not comfortable between pedagogical approach and action research. With students, the process is different. Where young people are approached, it is different.”

Ambivalence and discomfort

- Uncertainty for adult researchers – should AR with young people be *completely* free from adult intervention? What is the meaning of ‘action’ – what should the outcomes look like?

“Are we researchers or we are activists? We cannot be both.”

“Is this youth work or action research? What are we doing?”

- Also uncomfortable to experience first-hand the contradictions and injustices of young people’s struggles for participation.
- Reflects the experience of youth workers?

The training module

- A contribution to the education and training of youth workers and other professionals, as well as for students of youth policy and practice.
- Based on the distinctive learning from the process and findings of the Partispace research – all of it!
- Organised in eight linked units, with readings from the Partispace research, activities and assessment tasks running through the whole module.
- Designed to be used for self-directed or group learning, and to be adaptable to local contexts.

Learning objectives

1. To develop an understanding of the wide range of activities, styles and spaces that can be considered as youth participation.
2. To learn about the biographical and contextual factors that enable or encourage youth participation.
3. To reflect critically on issues of power, autonomy and control in participatory groups and activities involving young people.
4. To achieve a better understanding of the role of the worker in supporting young people's participation and autonomous action.

Methods of learning

- Strong emphasis on interaction, reflection and dialogue – with fellow students, with colleagues, with the literature and with the examples from the Partispace research.
- Opportunity to pursue a practice-based project and to offer that for the final assessment, as well as an essay-based assignment.

The eight units

- Unit 1: What is participation?
- Unit 2: Who participates?
- Unit 3: Whose agenda? Power and democracy in groups
- Unit 4: Participation as political agency and social action
- Unit 5: Participation as learning and self-developing
- Unit 6: Participation as community and belonging
- Unit 7: The role of the worker
- Unit 8: Reflections, implications and final assessment

To sum up...

- We have learned so much from this project about the different forms that participation can take and the different ways in which it can be understood.
- Much of this learning has been theoretical, but the practical implications are at least equally important.
- The experience of Work Package 5 has brought us in touch directly with the experience of adults charged with the task of supporting youth participation – or at least not getting in the way!
- In the training module we have tried to reflect this experience and to assist those working with young people to learn from it.

PARTISPACE

SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Empowering Youth Participation

Policy recommendations from PARTISPACE

Janet Batsleer, Manchester Metropolitan University

*“Youth Participation in Europe – Diversity, (Mis)Recognition, (In)Visibility”,
Final conference of PARTISPACE, Paris 18th of April 2018*

www.partispace.eu

PARTISPACE
SPACES AND STYLES OF PARTICIPATION

Doubts and thoughts from a researcher's perspective

- Ambivalence, tokenism and fakery of participation
- Are we acting as best we can to improve the current situation through compromise ...
- or do we seek to support non-political acts and enlarge a space of charity, civility and social action that can remain uncontaminated by politics?
- Or do we seek to imagine a quite new way of being, of participating by rejecting existing patterns,?

Impressions from gazing around 1

“I think in a certain way you can relate politics to our living here [in the residential care home] ... There are rules which limit the young people and there are always discussions about the rules, how to change them, and to find compromises and one can say this is a compressed political system.” (Biographical interview, Simon, case study residential care Frankfurt)

Impressions from gazing around 2

„The volunteers are active literally all around the city – the City Centre, the Central Park, the rowing base, the Hospital, public soup-kitchens, in front of churches, stores, and schools. They occupy new territories and construct their own space; they fill the urban infrastructure with new meanings. They adjust parts of the City Garden for the Anti-AIDS campaign, put tents, tables, materials, use the ledge of the Fountain in front of the Municipality ... they are making a micro-difference, a small change. In their accounts, the participants gradually outline a spirit of charity dominated by the motivation of helping others (Field note, case study humanitarian NGO, Plovdiv)

1. From Invitation to Recognition

- Young people are already active in public space but not all activity is recognised as participation
- Experiences of recognition make the difference in
 - Power and self-efficacy
 - Getting involved
 - Opening for interests and claims of others

→ Recognise young people's activities in public space as claims and attempts of being part of society

2. Resources for diverse activities

- Most financial resources are spent prioritising specific styles of youth culture and participation
 - Local youth policies must balance infrastructure and responsiveness
 - Fund spaces that are open and adequate for diversity of youth and styles
 - Distribute funds directly to different groups in a transparent and flexible way
 - EU youth policy may revitalise funding youth initiatives

3. Spaces

- Young people's activities in the public spaces are ways of appropriating the city
- Fostering participation needs to be interpreted as providing access to (diversity of) spaces
 - Allow for the use of abandoned spaces
 - Tolerate different forms of using public space
 - Provide an infrastructure of open youth work as spaces for appropriation
 - Turn public institutions into 'breathing spaces'

4. Conflicts

- Diversity implies conflicting ideas and interests
 - between young people and adults as well as among young people
 - About use of money and in appropriation of space
- Accept conflicts as moments of participation
- rather than ascribing them to deficits and lack of competencies for ‘right’ participation
 - and criminalising and stigmatising them as deviant
- Provide spaces in which conflicts can be expressed and performed

5. Learning participation

- Participation and democracy are learned by doing – and by experience of recognition while doing
- Recognition of different activities in public space as participation allows reflecting them and understanding oneself as participating
 - Make (formal) participation free from conditions how to participate and to learn ,right‘ participation first
 - Keep youth work free from agendas and curricula but understand it as ,hub for appropriation and recognition‘
 - Change school from providing citizenship education to a place of lived democracy (without limits)

6. Empower youth policies and mainstream youth in other policies

- Youth policies tend to be subordinate to other policy areas (social policies, education, labour market)
 - Access to welfare and education as powerful sign and means of participation
 - Empower youth policy allowing for the development of a youth work infrastructure
 - ... while keeping it reflexive for responsiveness
 - Mainstreaming youth participation in other policy areas addressing youth
 - EU must increase pressure on member states and ...
 - ... make participation a 'hard' criterion of funding in Youth on the Move and Youth Guarantee

7. Power needs Rights: towards a European Charter of Youth Rights

- Participation is about sharing power
 - It must not depend on policy culture, attitudes of youth workers and competences of young people
 - Children's rights are promoted by the UN but young people have different life situations, needs and interests
- A European Charter of Youth Rights is needed
- ... developed by and with young people
 - ... as a platform and living document
 - ... coordinated by the Youth Partnership